

Thiazole Compounds

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In connection with the previous work on thiazole compounds¹, the condensation of rubeanic acid (one mole) with α -bromoketones (2 moles), gave the corresponding dithiazolyl products. In the present investigation, the work was extended to include certain α -bromoketones such as: phenacylbromide², 4-bromoacetyl biphenyl³, 2-bromoacetyl fluorene⁴, and 5-bromoacetyl indane. On condensation of these α -bromoketones with rubeanic acid the following compounds were obtained respectively:

Dithiazolyls generally show intense fluorescence and are halochromic; but these four dithiazolyl compounds do not show any fluorescence, neither in daylight nor in UV light.

EXPERIMENTAL

A solution of 0.01 mole rubeanic acid in a suitable solvent, usually ethanol or dioxane, was mixed with a solution of 0.02 mole α -bromoketones in the same solvent. The mixture was kept under continuous reflux for 5 hr. About 30 minutes after refluxing, the condensation product started to separate. It was cooled, filtered, washed repeatedly with cold ethanol and ether, and then dried. Recrystallization from benzene resulted in the formation of the pure compound.

1. *This Journal*, 1962, **39**, (9), 651; 1967, **44**, (9), 800-1.
2. Clibbens, Nierenstein, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1915, **107**, 1492.
3. Long, Henze, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1941, **63**, 1939.
4. Ssolonina, *Chem. Zentr.*, 1905, **1**, 343.

The data for each compound and the slight variation in the experimental condition of its preparation are shown in the following table.

TABLE I

Reaction medium	Name of the product	colour	m.p. °C	yield	molecular formula	C%		Analysis H%		N%	
						found	calcd.	found	calcd.	found	calcd.
Ethanol	1,1'-(diphenyl)-2, dithiazolyl (I)	bright green needles	216	2.3 g. 73%	$C_{18}H_{12}N_2S_2$	67.62	67.47	3.84	3.77	8.66	8.74
Dioxane	4,4'-(dibiphenyl)-2,2'-dithiazolyl (II)	yellowish crystals	228	33 g. 70%	$C_{30}H_{20}N_2S_2$	76.42	76.24	4.31	4.26	5.90	5.92
Dioxane	2,2'-(difluoryl)-2, 2'-dithiazolyl (III)	yellow crystals	230	3.8 g. 75%	$C_{32}H_{20}N_2S_2$	77.48	77.38	4.16	4.06	5.74	5.64
Ethanol	5,5'-(diindyl)-2, 2'-dithiazolyl (IV)	yellowish crystals	210	2.5 g. 65%	$C_{24}H_{20}N_2S_2$	72.05	71.96	4.95	5.03	6.95	6.99

All melting points are uncorrected and were measured on Kofler block. Micro-analysis was carried out by Alfred Bernhardt, Max-Planck Institute, Ruhr, West Germany.

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